

ENGLISH PROVERBS WITH PROPER NAMES

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Abstract. The present article is devoted to investigation of proper names in the structure of proverbs of the English language. Theoretical content of the article is proved by numerous examples. The author gives information about different semantic groups of English proverbs with proper names.

Key word: proverb, proper name, onomastics, semantics, meaning, image.

Аннотация. Настоящая статья посвящается исследованию имён собственных в структуре пословиц английского языка. Теоретическое содержание статьи подтверждается многочисленными примерами. Автор представляет информацию о разных семантических группах английских пословицах с именами собственными.

Ключевые слова: пословица, имя собственное, ономастика, семантика, значение, образ.

Аннотация. Мазкур мақола инглиз тилидаги мақолнинг структурасида атоқли отларнинг қўлланишининг тадқиқи бағишланган. Мақоланинг назарий мазмуни кўплаб мисоллар билан далилланган. Мақолада структурасида атоқли отлар қўлланилган инглиз мақолларнинг турли семантик гуруҳлар ҳақида маълумот тақдим этилган.

Калит сўзлар: мақол, атоқли от, ономастика, семантика, маъно, образ.

A name is simply a word, phrase or sentence by which a human being is by it, he or she is identified, called, described, distinguished and classified. Nothing on earth and in much of the heavens exists without a name...A name conveys history, culture, heritage, language and a consciousness of self-image and pride. Onomastics (study of names) involves many disciplines such as history, geography, linguistics, literature, philosophy, anthropology, psychology, sociology, theology, and even the legal and medical sciences... [2, p.16-17].

A few proverbs with proper names are listed below. Note that proverbs may exist in several variants, for example: I fear the Greeks even when bringing gifts; I fear the Greeks bringing gifts; I fear the Greeks bearing gifts. Because proverbs are widely known, people often say just part of a proverb, like an idiomatic expression, for example: Greek gifts; Greek gift (i.e. a gift from an enemy may be dangerous). Russian translation of the proverbs below is approximate, and in some cases a corresponding Russian proverb is given instead.

All roads lead to Rome.

Все дороги ведут в Рим.
All work and no play makes Jack a dull boy.
Работа без отдыха отупляет человека.
An Englishman's home is his castle.
Дом англичанина - его крепость.
April showers bring forth May flowers.
Ливни в апреле родят цветы в мае.
Bacchus has drowned more men than Neptune.
Бахус (Вакх) утопил больше людей, чем Нептун.
Caesar's wife must be above suspicion.
Жена Цезаря должна быть выше подозрений.
East or West, home is best.
В гостях хорошо, а дома лучше.
I fear the Greeks even when bringing gifts.
Боюсь греков (данайцев), даже приносящих дары.
If the mountain will not come to Mahomet, Mahomet must go to the mountain.
Если гора не идет к Магомету, Магомет должен идти к горе.
Jack of all trades is master of none.
Тот, кто умеет все, ни в чем не специалист.
March comes in like a lion and goes out like a lamb.
Март приходит как лев, а уходит как ягненок.
Render to Caesar the things that are Caesar's.
Кесарю кесарево.
Rome was not built in a day.
Рим не за один день был построен.
Too far East is West.
Противоположности сходятся.
When in Rome, do as the Romans do.
В чужой монастырь со своим уставом не ходят.

Proverbs, in colorful and vivid language, reflect important typical cultural values of every culture. Simple and popular, concise and pithy, they are passed on from generation to generation in the readable oral form and have gradually become a component indispensable to the dominant culture of that nation [1, p. 32].

This chapter contains three parts: the sources of English proverbs, the functions of English proverbs and the rhetorical devices of English proverbs. Firstly, it introduces the sources of English proverbs.

Proverbs have a long history. They are brief and well-polished expressions embedded in philosophical ideas concerning different aspects of life. They are the summary of people experience in everyday life, so they originated from people's daily life and experience. To be specific, they come from folk life, religion, mythology, literary works, other languages, famous writers' wisdom, a nation's history and so on.

Secondly, it mentions the function of English proverbs. Its function is to teach and advise people what they see in their lives. Many English proverbs guide people to adopt a correct attitude towards life and to take a proper way to get along well with others. Some other proverbs tell people what to do and how to do it, so the proverbs guide people's daily life. From them, people may broaden their knowledge and outlook.

Thirdly, it describes their rhetorical devices. English proverbs are rich and colorful. With regard to the everlasting charm of the English proverbs, there are many different reasons. The most important one is the extensive use of rhetorical devices and rhythmical ways, so their language is full of image and vividness and has a strong artistic beauty and power.

Proverbs colorful, vivid, meaningful, reflecting each nation is geared to the important and unique cultural values. Simple and popular proverbs, and brilliantly concise, particularly in the oral form of language heritage in use, and gradually become a national an indispensable part of mainstream culture. English Proverbs has a long history of human experience, the crystallization of everyday life. It derives from the daily life and experience, rather, from civilian life, religion, myth, literature, other languages, famous celebrities and national history.

Proverbs' function is to educate and guide people in their daily lives is the case, and they lead people to adopt a correct attitude towards life. From the proverb, people can broaden their knowledge to avoid making mistakes, with keen observation of people stand to benefit greatly. English proverbs colorful, with the eternal charm, one of the reasons is the application of a lot of rhetoric and rhyme lattice method, which makes the image of proverbial more vivid and have a strong artistic beauty and infection force [3, p.107].

Proverbs are short sayings of folk wisdom of well-known facts or truths compendious expressed and in a way that makes them easy to remember. Because the proverbs are so brief, they have universal appeal. Many people love to pick up proverbs. The use of one or two in the original language is often a minor victory for the beginning foreign language learners. Proverbs may provide

interesting little glimpses or clues to a people's geography, history, Social organization, social views, and attitudes. People who live along seacoasts and whose livelihood is dependent on the sea will have proverbs about sailing, about braving the weather, about fish and fishing. In cultures where old age is revered, there will be proverbs about the wisdom of the elders. And in societies where women's status is low, there will be a number of sayings demeaning them.

Proverbs tell much about a people's traditional ways of experiencing reality, about the proper or expected ways of doing things, about values and warnings, and rules and wisdoms the elders want to impress on the minds of their young. The important character of proverbs' the shorter the better 'makes it easy to commit them to memory for ready recall when the occasion calls for serious or humorous comment or warning. Created by people in high and low status, humble folk and great authors, borrowed from ancient or neighboring cultures, proverbs have been accumulating over many centuries. Some are only locally known; many are shared around the world. If one wants to have better knowledge of English culture, he should be familiar with the sources and functions of English proverbs.

Literature:

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